

CELLULOSE NANOFIBRILS AS FUNCTIONAL ADDITIVES IN BIO-BASED BARRIER COATINGS FOR PAPER PACKAGING

Patricija Pevec¹, Urška Kavčič¹, Janja Juhant Grkman², Panu Lahtinen³, Urban Svoltjšak⁴

¹Pulp and Paper Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²KANSAI HELIOS Kemostik d.o.o., Kamnik, Slovenia

³VTT, Espoo, Finland

⁴Goričane d.d., Medvode, Slovenia

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17294678

patricija.pevec@icp-lj.si

Abstract: Sustainable fiber-based packaging materials are primarily produced from renewable materials that have high recyclability. Nevertheless, to achieve barrier properties required for food packaging applications, paper and cardboards are often laminated or coated. Conventional barrier coatings that are currently in use are still mostly fossil-based, highlighting the need to develop sustainable coating solutions for fiber-based materials. Cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) that has large specific area and ability to form strong network structures via hydrogen bonding is a promising material for improvement of mechanical as well as barrier properties. While CNF can be obtained also from alternative biomass sources, in the SuperBark project we aim to produce CNF from bark and use it in bio-based coatings to achieve barrier properties for food packaging papers. To evaluate the bark-based CNF used in these kinds of applications, the barrier coating solutions with starch and bleached or unbleached bark-based CNF were developed and applied on three different base papers. Barrier properties of rod coated samples were evaluated regarding water vapour transition rate (WVTR) and grease resistance. Subsequent mechanical evaluation of the coated samples was performed. The research has confirmed that the starch coating increase barrier as well as mechanical properties on all three paper samples. However, the addition of bark-based CNF into starch coating increased the water vapour barrier at 85% relative humidity and was crucial to achieve the highest KIT 12 grease resistance and better mechanical properties on Paper 3.

Keywords: barrier coating development, barrier packaging material, CNF, sustainable packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

Food packaging manufacturers often utilize fossil-based materials or fiber-based materials that are (extrusion) coated or laminated, typically with materials which are neither non-biodegradable nor biobased, to increase their barrier properties. The pressure on packaging manufacturers to replace non-biodegradable plastics has become a global trend at both academic and industrial level. To overachieve these unsustainable practices, greener and more renewable solutions and materials could be developed and used for barrier packaging materials. Enhancing papers resistance to moisture, grease and air by aqueous coating suspensions presents one of the possibilities. (Mazega et al., 2022) Besides that, utilization of environmentally more acceptable and biodegradable materials like cellulose and its derivatives could be an option. The challenge of attaining paper-based materials with barrier properties comparable to those obtained by plastic remains ongoing, despite the latest efforts of researchers. A key limitation is that most biopolymers are hydrophilic in nature and thus the performance is highly affected by the relative humidity of the environment. (Hamdani et al., 2020) To

improve the water barrier property and mechanical stability of cellulose materials, hydrophobic modification strategies provide a barrier to wettability and offer low permeability to moisture. (Asim et al., 2022) Recent advancements highlight nanocellulose, especially CNF, as a biocompatible and biodegradable coating that enhances paper's density, mechanical strength, resistance to moisture and air permeability, making it suitable for food contact and thermal processing conditions. (Lengowski et al., 2023) CNF can improve aqueous suspensions encompassing water-insoluble components both as rheology modifier and as stabilizer. (Zheng et al., 2022) They have also been used as coating components and are well-known to increase the air resistance of paper by esterification with sizing agents (Alkyl Ketene Dimer (AKD), Alkenyl Succinic Anhydride (ASA)) commonly used in papermaking. (Mazega et al., 2022) Mazega et al. discovered, that coating paper sheets with CNF effectively decreased papers oil-wicking ability and increased KIT rating. The air resistance was also improved by two orders of magnitude. Anyway, the surface became more hydrophilic. (Mazega et al., 2022) In the study of Lengowski et al., CNF was produced from bleached eucalyptus pulp and applied in two wet thicknesses (1 mm and 2 mm) onto unbleached Pinus-based kraft paper. They prepared and analysed coated paper and standalone CNF films, examining their morphological, physical, mechanical, and thermal properties. CNF effectively filled the pores in the kraft paper surface, resulting in a denser, smoother, and less permeable structure. Water absorption and air permeance were significantly reduced on the coated side, while mechanical properties (particularly bursting and tensile strength) increased markedly with CNF application. Although films alone had high tensile strength, they lacked tearing resistance due to fibril morphology. All materials, including coated papers, met thermal stability requirements for food contact. (Lengowski et al., 2023) Lyytikäinen et al. explored the barrier performance of multilayered cellulose-based coatings (specifically methyl nanocellulose (MeNC), microfibrillated cellulose (MFC), and hydrophobically modified cellulose (HM-EHEC)). The study systematically evaluated the effects of varying coat weights and layering strategies on key properties such as surface morphology, wettability, oil and grease resistance (OGR), and oxygen transmission rate (OTR) under diverse temperature and humidity conditions. The inclusion of HM-EHEC enhanced hydrophobicity, particularly under elevated humidity. Notably, coating structures that combined all three components achieved complete surface sealing and high barrier performance, even at high temperatures and relative humidities, suggesting their strong potential in replacing synthetic barriers for food packaging applications. (Lyytikäinen et al., 2025)

While CNF offer many possibilities and advantageous in the field of fiber-based packaging materials, in the presented research, coating solutions with starch and starch with addition of bleached as well as unbleached bark-based CNF were prepared and applied on three different base papers. The aim of the study was to investigate the influence of bark-based CNF on barrier (water vapour, grease) and mechanical properties of all (un)coated samples.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the scope of this research different base papers were firstly analysed, then coated with different coating solutions containing starch and bark-based CNF. Finally, barrier properties of the coated samples were determined.

As a base papers, three papers (Paper 1, Paper 2, Paper 3) produced by Goričane d.d. papermill were selected and evaluated regarding grammage (ISO 536), thickness (ISO 534), filler content (ISO 1762), Bendtsen smoothness (ISO 8791-2) and Bendtsen porosity (ISO 5636-3). Beside basic properties also the surfaces of the base papers were evaluated using scanning electron microscope (SEM) Jeol 6060 LV (Jeol, Japan).

To evaluate the influence of coating on barrier properties of the coated papers, three different coating formulations were prepared and applied on the surfaces of the papers. The base of the coating formulations was thermally modified, commercially available starch (Stabilys EVO 280, Roquette) to

which two different bleached and unbleached bark-based CNFs (VTT, Finland) were added to analyse the influence of CNF type on barrier properties.

2.1 Samples preparation

Firstly, (1) thermally modified starch coating with 20% concentration was prepared. The dry starch was mixed with water and cooked for 30 minutes, then allowed to cool down to 30–40 °C. After cooling, nanocellulose was incorporated into the mixture. To determine the influence of unbleached and bleached bark-based CNF on the barrier properties, two additional coating solutions were prepared. Initially (2) starch-based coating with addition of 3% bleached bark-based CNF VTT24 was prepared and finally, (3) starch-based coating with addition of 3% unbleached bark-based CNF VTT20. The final concentration of coating solutions with bark-based CNF was 20%.

One layer (10 g/m²) of the developed coating solutions were applied on the surfaces of the base papers with laboratory rod coater (RK Print Coater, UK) and dried 1 minute at 105°C in ventilation oven.

The coated samples were evaluated regarding water vapour and grease resistance. The water vapour transition rate (WVTR) was analysed according to ISO 2528 standard at two different conditions (50% RH at 23°C and 85% RH at 23°C). Grease resistance was assessed using the KIT test according to TAPPI T559 cm.

Besides barrier properties, all the samples were evaluated also regarding mechanical properties. Tensile strength was determined in accordance with ISO 1924-2 standard using Zwick/Roell Z010 multi testing device (Zwick/Roell, Germany).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All three selected base papers were firstly analysed regarding basic paper properties. As can be seen from *Table 1*, all samples have similar grammage (around 50 g/m²), Paper 1 and Paper 2 have almost the same thickness (67 and 68 µm) while Paper 3 is thinner (57 µm). The main difference between the papers is in filler content (Paper 1 is without filler, Paper 2 and Paper 3 have 7% filler content). Additionally, Paper 3 also has a precoat, that decreases smoothness as well as porosity of the paper.

Table 1: Basic properties of selected base papers

Paper property	Paper 1	Paper 2	Paper 3
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	50.7	50.3	51.2
<i>Thickness (µm)</i>	67	68	57
<i>Filler at 500°C (%)</i>	/	7	7
<i>Smoothness Bendtsen (ml/min)</i>	280	235	90
<i>Porosity Bendtsen (ml/min)</i>	125	310	90
<i>Type of sizing agent</i>	AKD	Rosin sizing agent	Rosin sizing agent

The evaluation of the base papers with scanning electron microscope (SEM) provides a clear demonstration of the base paper's surfaces with visible filler in Paper 2 and precoat on the surface of Paper 3 (Figure 1:1).

Paper 1

Paper 2

Paper 3

Figure 1: SEM images (500× magnification) of the surfaces of the base papers.

The basic properties as well as SEM images of the paper’s surface offer the important insight for understanding further evaluation of applied coatings on the paper samples.

After the coating application, water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) was determined on starch coated (EVO 280) and starch with CNF (EVO 280 + VTT24, EVO 280 + VTT20) coated samples (Figure 2). The application of EVO 280 starch alone significantly decreased WVTR across all paper substrates, confirming its effectiveness as a moisture barrier under both humidity conditions. While the addition of CNF in the coating did not result in substantial further improvements at 50% RH, enhancements were observed under more challenging conditions at 85% RH. Notably, Paper 3, which contains fillers and precoat, exhibited the greatest improvement when combined with unbleached CNF (VTT20), suggesting synergistic effects between the filler and CNF in enhancing the moisture barrier. Furthermore, a marked difference in performance was observed between the two CNFs tested: bleached VTT24 showed limited benefit, whereas unbleached VTT20 significantly improved the barrier properties—reducing WVTR on Paper 3 from 310 g/m²/24h (starch EVO 280 only) to approximately 200 g/m²/24h (EVO 280 + VTT20).

Figure 2: WVTR of uncoated and coated paper samples at 50% RH and 85% RH.

Similarly, the influence of coating on grease resistance is obvious when the samples were coated with starch only (from KIT 0 to KIT 4 on Paper 1 and KIT 7 on Paper 2 and Paper 3), however with addition of CNF into the coating solutions, the grease resistance increases significantly. From Figure one can observe that on Paper 1, that has no filler and precoat, the maximum KIT value 9 is achieved when bleached CNF was added to the starch coating. Filler in Paper 2 improved grease resistance, while with addition of bleached or unbleached CNF increase KIT value to 11. The best grease resistance was achieved on Paper 3, where KIT value increased from KIT 7 (starch coating) to KIT 12, when (bleached or unbleached) CNF was added into the coating solution.

Figure 3: KIT values of uncoated and coated paper samples.

The tensile properties of the samples are presented in Figure 4 and Table 2. The stress–strain curves provide insight into the mechanical response under loading, while the Table 2 parameters summarize the elongation and stress at break. The uncoated Paper 1 showed the highest strength, with maximum stresses at break among uncoated papers (58.93 MPa) together with a moderate elongation at break of 2.57%. Paper 2 presented intermediate behaviour while Paper 3 was the weakest substrate, with stresses at break around 40 MPa, and elongation of 1.67%. These results of mechanical evaluation of the uncoated samples reflect the composition of the base papers (Paper 1 as the mechanically strongest, Paper 2 as intermediate, and Paper 3 as the weakest substrate). Starch coating improved the tensile performance of all papers. In the stress–strain curves, the coated papers generally followed the shape of the uncoated ones, but reached higher forces at a given strain. Paper 1 increased elongation from 2.57% to 3.56%, while Paper 2 improved from 1.53% to 1.89% elongation. Paper 3 showed the strongest relative response, with elongation increasing from 1.67% to 2.22%. Stronger substrate (Paper 1), shows only marginal improvement with addition of CNF, while weaker substrate (Paper 3) benefit substantially from the reinforcement, particularly with the bleached CNF (VTT24). Starch coating consistently improves all papers, mainly by increasing elongation, while CNF provides additional strength and stiffness, with VTT20 being more effective for Paper 2 and VTT24 for Paper 3.

These findings are in line with the results of Lengowski et al. (2023), who also observed improved tensile performance when applying CNF coatings, particularly in substrates with lower initial strength. The addition of CNF to starch further modified the tensile response. In Paper 1, both coatings slightly increased elongation compared to the uncoated substrate (3.20–3.36%). Paper 2, in contrast, benefited more from the nanocellulose addition: EVO280+VTT20 yielded the best performance, with stress at break above 40 MPa, exceeding both the uncoated and starch-only conditions. For Paper 3, the weakest substrate, EVO280+VTT24 increased stress at break from 40 to 41 MPa, as well as showing enhanced strength in the force–strain curves, especially beyond 1% strain. These results confirm that the effectiveness of the coatings is substrate-dependent and align well with Lyytikäinen et al. (2025), who reported that multilayered cellulose-based coatings, particularly those including modified CNF, exhibited strong barrier and reinforcement effects under challenging environmental conditions.

Figure 4: Tensile stress/strain curves of uncoated and coated samples on three papers

Table 2: Tensile properties of papers without and with coatings

	Paper 1	Paper1 + EVO280	Paper1 +EVO280 +VTT20	Paper1 +EVO280 +VTT24	Paper 2	Paper2 +EVO280	Paper2 +EVO280 +VTT20	Paper2 +EVO280 +VTT24	Paper 3	Paper3 +EVO280	Paper3 +EVO280 +VTT20	Paper3 +EVO280 +VTT24
Strain [%]	2.57	3.56	3.36	3.20	1.53	1.89	1.99	2.04	1.67	2.22	2.15	2.09
Stress at break [MPa]	58.93	60.50	56.33	55.53	41.07	43.96	43.53	46.71	40.02	38.89	37.28	40.99

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study confirmed that bio-based coatings provide improvements to both barrier and mechanical properties of paper substrates, supporting their potential as sustainable alternatives to plastic laminates in food packaging. Starch alone enhanced tensile strength, elongation, and barrier properties across all substrates, while the addition of bark-based CNF further reinforced the papers in a substrate-dependent manner. Unbleached bark-based CNF (VTT20) proved most effective for Paper 2, whereas bleached CNF (VTT24) gave the strongest reinforcement in the weakest substrate Paper 3. The highest influence on barrier properties was achieved with starch coating alone, however, the influence of addition of bark-based CNF on WVTR at 85% RH was promising and additionally improved barrier (especially on Paper 3). Similar influence of bark-based CNF was observed also with grease resistance, where CNF evidently increase the KIT value. The highest grease barrier (KIT 12) on Paper 3 was achieved solely due to the addition of bark-based CNF into the starch coating. These results are consistent with previous research on CNF coatings and demonstrate that tailoring coating formulations to the characteristics of the base paper is essential for achieving optimal performance. Overall, starch (with addition of nanocellulose) coatings represent a promising strategy to advance bio-based and biodegradable paper packaging solutions.

Acknowledgments: The SuperBark project (grant agreement No. 101112447) is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

5 REFERENCES

- Asim, N., Badiei, M., & Mohammad, M. (2022). Recent advances in cellulose-based hydrophobic food packaging. In *Emergent Materials* (Vol. 5, Issue 3, pp. 703–718). Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42247-021-00314-2>
- Hamdani, S. S., Li, Z., Sirinakbumrung, N., & Rabnawaz, M. (2020). Zein and PVOH-Based Bilayer Approach for Plastic-Free, Repulpable and Biodegradable Oil- And Water-Resistant Paper as a Replacement for Single-Use Plastics. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, 59(40), 17856–17866. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.0c02967>
- Lengowski, E. C., Bonfatti Júnior, E. A., Coelho Simon, L., de Muniz, G. I., de Andrade, A., Neves Leite, A., & de Miranda Leite, E. L. (2023). Nanocellulose Coating on Kraft Paper. *Coatings*, 13(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13101705>
- Lyytikäinen, J., Koljonen, K., & Leminen, V. (2025). Effects of multilayered cellulose-based coatings on the barrier properties of paperboard. *Cellulose*, 32(4), 2617–2628. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-025-06416-y>
- Mazega, A., Tarrés, Q., Aguado, R., Pèlach, M. À., Mutjé, P., Ferreira, P. J. T., & Delgado-Aguilar, M. (2022). Improving the Barrier Properties of Paper to Moisture, Air, and Grease with Nanocellulose-Based Coating Suspensions. *Nanomaterials*, 12(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12203675>
- Zheng, Y., Oguzlu, H., Baldelli, A., Zhu, Y., Song, M., Pratap-Singh, A., & Jiang, F. (2022). Sprayable cellulose nanofibrils stabilized phase change material Pickering emulsion for spray coating application. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2022.119583>